

ACUTE MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION AFTER BLUNT CHEST TRAUMA IN A YOUNG PATIENT

Keywords

Blunt Chest

Trauma,

Chest Pain,

Ventricular Fibrillation,

Myocardial Infarction

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ABSTRACT

Heart attacks are among the most important preventable emergencies that require urgent intervention and diagnosis, which are frequently encountered in emergency departments. Blunt chest trauma can cause injuries to the coronary artery through various mechanisms, such as vascular spasm, dissection, and intimal tear or rupture of an existing thrombus. In patients with multiple traumas from a car accident, chest pain may be masked by other injuries. In this case, we will present a rare cause of STEMI after a car accident in a young patient. An 18-year-old male with no specific medical history had a car accident at a speed of 50 km/h and was injured in the chest with the steering wheel of the car. He had chest pain and superficial wounds after the accident. Immediately ECG revealed to patient and ST elevation in V1-V6 and D1 and avL was seen. He was thus diagnosed with extensive anterior ST elevation MI. He was referred to our center for angiography. Coronary angiography showed total occlusion in the coronary artery and stenting. After 2 days the patient was discharged with full recovery.

INTRODUCTION

Heart attacks are among the most important preventable emergencies that require urgent intervention and diagnosis, which are frequently encountered in emergency departments. Patients with suspected cardiac disease should have a rapid ECG.(1) STEMI (ST eleve myocardial infarction) is one of the most common life-threatening conditions encountered in ECG.The main objective of managing STEMI is to decrease the risk of mortality and the extent of permanent cardiac injury associated with myocardial infarction. Because therapy for patients with STEMI becomes less effective with each passing minute, it is crucial to rapidly treat patients with STEMI before treatment becomes ineffective¹.

Blunt chest trauma can cause injuries to the coronary artery through various mechanisms, such as vascular spasm, dissection, and intimal tear or rupture of an existing thrombus². In patients with multiple traumas from a car accident, chest pain may be masked by other injuries.

CASE

An 18-year-old male with no specific medical history had a car accident at a speed of 50 km/h and was injured in the chest with the steering wheel of the car. He had chest pain and superficial wounds after the accident and was referred to the Emergency Department of On admission, he had severe chest pain and sweating at rest, and his blood pressure was 120/70 mmHg and heart rate was 90 bpm. Immediately ECG revealed to patient and ST elevation in V1-V6 and D1 and avL was seen. He had dynamic ST-T changes He was thus diagnosed with extensive anterior ST elevation MI. On follow up, ventricular fibrillation was observed on the monitor and the patient was defibrillated. A second ECG was performed after defibrillation. After echocardiography (EF= 40-45%) he was referred to our center for angiography. Coronary angiography showed total occlusion in the coronary artery and stenting. After 2 days the patient was discharged with full recovery.

DISCUSSION

History, physical examination, ECG and serial measurement of troponin are the cornerstone of the evaluation of patients with suspected MI after blunt chest trauma³. The majority of blunt cardiac injuries are the result of rapid deceleration and trauma caused by high-speed motor vehicle

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accidents. One of the most common scenarios is damage to the chest from the steering wheel axis when the car comes to a sudden stop for an unrestrained driver in a high speed motor vehicle collision. Less common causes include a direct blow to the front of the chest, falls from a height, and sports-related accidents⁴.

Most patients with blunt chest trauma complain of dyspnea or chest pain. Also, in the vast majority of these patients, only the minor injuries are causing the pain; some would have serious underlying conditions that would require specific therapies. Cardiac pain may be masked by various injuries, so a high index of clinical suspicion is required⁵. After blunt trauma to the chest, it is important to consider the possibility of injury to the coronary artery^{5,6}.

CONCLUSION

This condition is often underdiagnosed and can be difficult to diagnose due to chest pain being interpreted as secondary to chest wall contusion or being overshadowed by other injuries. Diagnosis of coronary dissection after chest trauma requires clinical suspicion and systematic evaluation. Electrocardiography (ECG) should be performed on every patient with thoracic trauma, as clinical findings may be misleading.

Conflict of interest

No conflict of interest is reported by the authors.

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No

Image 1. EKG at admission showing ST-segment elevation in D1, aVL, V1, V2. And also reciprocal ST segment depression in D2, D3, aVF present. EKG, electrocardiogram

Image 2. After defibrillation second EKG showing extend anterolateral ST-segment elevation in D1, aVL, V1, V2, V3, V4, V5. And also reciprocal ST segment depression in D2, D3, aVF present. EKG, electrocardiogram

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